

THE IMPLEMENTATION AND EXPLORATION OF FANTASY IN
UZBEK LITERATURE

Madaminova S. A

The teacher of department of English language

"Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and Agricultural Mechanization Engineers"

National Research University

Annotation: Theoretical and scientific support of the existence of fiction in Eastern literature is regarded as an integral part of world classical literature. It influences and relies on not only elements of fiction in Uzbek classical literature, but also mature examples, the development of modern Uzbek fiction, in particular, science fiction as well as the study of problems is evaluated as a great scientific importance.

Key words: drama, cybernetics, electronics, atomic and nuclear processes, literature, science fiction, immemorial, uphology, Uzbek fiction, fantasy, phenomena

Uzbek literature has always considered the most important issues of society. This is especially evident after independence. The main reason why we look at contemporary literature is that we see a variety and variety of new trends and trends, styles and genres. This, in turn, is connected with the democratic processes taking place in the country, and most importantly, the freedom of expression, which is related to artistic creativity. In the 20th century, especially after the Second World War, science and technology began to play a huge role in the development of society. This, in turn, has led to the rapid growth of science fiction¹. Historical events like the management of atomic and nuclear processes, electronics, cybernetics, genetics, uphology, and the advent of the universe testify to the fact that science fiction is

¹ R. Ibrohimova. Voqelik va Fantastika. T.: "Muharrir". 2011. B. 5

right.² The scientific assumptions in it correctly define the main directions of science and technology development. It should be noted that science fiction is now out of the reach of science and technology and covers social and philosophical issues. The first science fiction work came to the world in Uzbek literature, 'The Child of the Sun', was written by Gani Jahongirov and published in 1969. Since then a number of science fiction novels, more than a hundred short stories and science fiction stories have been creating recently. In 1977-1980, the Council of Young Uzbek Fiction Writers was established in Tashkent in the editorial office of the magazine "Science and Life" and carried out effective work. In 1980, there was a fiction section under the Writers' Union of Uzbekistan.

It is categorized that the formation of science fiction corresponds to the era of development of socio-economic, scientific and technological progress in the social development of the second half of the 20th century. "At the end of the last century," writes Gerbert Wells, "no one was surprised, nobody believed in him and his results. At the same time, an idea came to my mind. Rather than confronting the reader with devil or jokes, magic, if you can imagine a little, you can follow the path that science has shown. That was not a great discovery. I just changed the old fetch to a new one. At an affordable level, I approached it with a true theory. "The glossy examples of science fiction in world literature can be found in Jules Verne and Gerbert Wells. Particularly, Tamazzo Campaigner's "City of the Sun" in 1623, Francis Bacon's "New Atlanta" created in 1627, Jonathan Swift's "Gulliver's Travels". In these works science and technology achievements, social development ideas are encouraged. However, as a network of fresh literature, as a new independent species, science fiction has developed in all aspects of J.Wern and G.Wells creativity³. It certainly influenced the national literature of other nations. Today, Uzbek folk artists like Mahkam Mahmudov, Tohir Malik, Hojiakbar Shaykhov, Murod Hidir and Anvar Kasimov are laying the foundations. Today, the culture and spiritual potential of our people is growing. We realize our self-esteem,

² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Fantasy_literature

³ [National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan](#) checked 25 March 2016

restore our national and spiritual-cultural values, and seek to find a worthy place in the world community. In the richness of the spiritual world, the role and place of literary literature is incomparable. As the types and genres of literary literature are diverse, the vital issues facing them are also this is due to the originality of each literary genre and genre, the image size and content, the plot and the composition. One of these interesting events in Uzbek literature is the birth of a science fiction. The concept of "fantasy" itself is very wide and complex, but also relative. The width of this concept is related to the diversity of species. When we talk about fiction, we understand science, art, and fantasy. In fact, the role of the fictional elements in artistic writing is determined by the outlook, genre, ideological aesthetic factors, as well as the way and nature of the writer's intentions. In general, science fiction has been classified into two main categories. This separation is categorized according to the way in which the fantasy was created. Of course, this classification is relative.

⁴The first of these is the phenomena and phenomena created by man or nature through science and technology. Second, miracles are created by natural forces. Of course, no matter how and when the science fiction has come into existence, it is primarily a form of real truth, a way to express the secrets of the universe, the origin of existence. It has emerged as a unique way of expressing life throughout its historical development, and has overcome a very complex and long-term development pathway associated with human consciousness growth. Of course, the emergence of scientific and technical progress, especially Jules Vern, played an important role in the formation of fiction literature. In Jules Vern's works, many discoveries and inventions have yet to be presented, which are still unfulfilled. After all, the discovery of a submarine, underwater skater at Captain Nemo alone led to the creation of technical inventions. Hence, artistic fiction has the ability to portray images of human beings as far as possible, known as the unthinking universe, possibly near or far from the great ocean, the boundless galaxies. Today, the science-fiction genre is developed not only for the developed European and American literature, but also in the Uzbek, Karakalpak, Kazakh, and Kyrgyz literature, which

⁴ R. Ibrohimova. Voqelik va Fantastika. T.: "Muharrir". 2011. B. 6

had never before had such an independent genre. The scientific and technological revolution of the formation of the science fiction genre in these publications is developing in the century, and also under the influence of the world science fiction. Today, the authors of fantasy writers like T.Malik, X. Shaykhov, M.Makhmudov, B. Hoshimxujayev and M. Khidir in the Uzbek literature are creating and writing. Despite the fact that well-known writers are the first fantasy, the Uzbek fantasy has not emerged from space. After all, the elements of science in the Uzbek literature have existed from the earliest times, in particular folklore, and have an ancient and rich history. It is one of the most pressing issues in our literary criticism to discover, analyze and expose the artistic abilities of this genre.

References:

1. М.Бакоева, Э.Муратова, М.Очилова. English Literature Toshkent-2010
2. R. Ibrohimova. Voqelik va Fantastika. T.: “Muharrir”. 2011
3. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Fantasy_literature
4. [National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan](#) checked 25 March 2016